

Processes controlling the upper ocean variability in the central Bay of Bengal on a seasonal time scale

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Abstract

The Bay of Bengal (BoB) has several distinct oceanographic features that make it a natural laboratory for learning about the interactions between the ocean and atmosphere. In spite of several past studies, a holistic understanding of the upper ocean variability is incomplete, mainly due to inadequate coverage of spatial data. Present study explores the seasonal cycle of the upper waters of the central BoB and its spatial structure using high-resolution spatial data from recently released World Ocean Atlas 2023. The upper ocean response was studied using monthly climatology of three surface parameters viz., sea surface temperature (SST), sea surface salinity (SSS) and sea surface density (SSD), and three subsurface parameters viz., isothermal layer thickness (ILT), mixed layer depth (MLD) and barrier layer thickness (BLT). A suite of data was used to determine atmospheric forcing via wind speed used as a proxy for momentum flux, net heat flux (NHF) and fresh water flux. All three surface and three subsurface parameters showed a seasonal cycle with bi-modal distribution of varying magnitudes. The processes that controlled the seasonal cycle of SST and ILT was the NHF and the wind speed. The seasonal cycle of SSS and BLT closely followed the freshwater flux and wind speed. The seasonal cycle of both SSD and MLD was regulated by NHF and wind during the winter monsoon, while freshwater flux and wind controlled it during summer monsoon. The role of cloud cover, which was hitherto unexplored, provided additional cooling mechanism during winter and summer monsoons via different processes. In summary, the study provides an in-depth understanding of how the latitudinal structure of the upper ocean's seasonal patterns vary and highlights the role of atmospheric forces, including cloud cover, in shaping this variability.

1. Introduction

The Bay of Bengal (BoB) is a tropical sea situated in the eastern part of the Northern Indian Ocean. It is the twelfth largest sea by surface area out of the seventy-six major seas of the world ocean (Fava, 2022). It is also one of the Large Marine Ecosystems

(LMEs) among the sixty-six LMEs of the world and accounts for 7% of the world's annual fish catch (Elayaperumal et al., 2019). Geographically, it is semi-enclosed by the land mass of Sri Lanka, India, Bangladesh, Myanmar and northern part of the Malay Peninsula and lies between 5° and 22° N latitudes (Morgan et al., 2024). It is land-locked in the north and open to the Equatorial Indian Ocean to the south. There are several distinct oceanographic features that make the BoB a unique tropical sea. One of them is the perineal presence of low-salinity waters in the upper layers of the BoB (Varkey et al., 1996; Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar, 2006). This is due to a combination of large freshwater influx of $1.625 \times 10^{12} \text{ m}^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Subramanian, 1993) from the rivers bordering the BoB (Durand et al., 2011) and excess precipitation over evaporation of 2 m year^{-1} (Prasad, 1997). The major rivers discharging freshwater into the BoB are Ganges, Brahmaputra, Irrawaddy, Mahanadi, Godavari, Krishna, Pennar, and Kaveri (Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar, 2006). This leads to the formation of barrier layer, a strong halocline within the upper isothermal layer (Lukas & Lindstrom, 1991; Sprintall & Tomczak, 1992), in the BoB (Vinayachandran et al., 2002; Thadathil et al., 2007; Kumari et al., 2018) and makes the upper water column highly stratified and difficult to mix (Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar, 2006). The presence of barrier layer limits the upward transfer of heat between mixed layer and thermocline which leads to the formation of subsurface thermal inversion (Thadathil et al., 2016). This happens during winter (November-February) when the surface waters are cooled and the barrier layer preserves the sub-surface warm waters (Kumari et al., 2018).

Another characteristic feature of the BoB is the omnipresence of cyclonic and anti-cyclonic eddies (Babu et al., 1991; Prasanna Kumar et al., 2004; Nuncio & Prasanna Kumar, 2012) in all the seasons (Prasanna Kumar et al., 2010) and occurrence of 3 to 5 tropical cyclones annually during pre-monsoon (April-May) and post-monsoon (October-December) seasons (Sikka, 2006). These cyclones though take a path usually to north-west direction and hit the east coast of India, they sometimes change their path to a north or north-east direction and hit Bangladesh and Myanmar coasts (Alam & Dominey-Howes, 2014). Both cyclonic eddies and tropical cyclones enhance primary production and chlorophyll biomass in the BoB by transferring the subsurface nutrient into the euphotic zone (Prasanna Kumar et al., 2004; Nuncio & Prasanna Kumar, 2012; Maneesha et al., 2019; Chowdhury et al., 2020). In-situ measurements using sediment trap recorded the mean annual flux of organic carbon at mid-depth, nominally at 1000m, in the BoB to be $26 \text{ gm}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Ramaswamy & Nair, 1994). The high sinking flux of organic carbon along with poor ventilation of waters create a strong oxygen minimum zone (OMZ) at mid-depths in the BoB. The OMZ in the BoB is the fourth major OMZ of the world ocean after the Eastern Tropical North Pacific, the Eastern Tropical South Pacific and the Arabian Sea (Stramma et al., 2008). However, unlike the other three OMZs large scale denitrification is not reported from the BoB (Naqvi, 1996).

The basin-scale dynamics and associated water circulation of the BoB is yet another

feature that is quite unique. Though the upper water of the BoB experience changes over a wide range of time-scales from intra-seasonal to inter-annual and multi-decadal, the most dominant mode of variability is seasonality (Potemra et al., 1991; Unnikrishnan et al., 1997; Eigenheer & Quadfasel, 2000). The strong seasonality experienced by the upper waters of the BoB is forced by the semi-annually reversing monsoon wind system, that changes from south-westerly during June to September (summer monsoon or southwest monsoon), to north-easterly during November to February (winter monsoon or northeast monsoon). It is not only the direction, but the strength of the wind also changes seasonally. For example, during June to September the winds are of oceanic origin blowing from south-westerly direction and transports warm and moisture laden maritime airmass into the BoB with an average speed of 10 m/s (Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar, 2006). In contrast, during November to February the winds are of continental origin blowing from north-easterly direction and transports cold and dry airmass into the BoB with an average speed of 5 m/s (Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar, 2006). During spring (March to May) and fall (September-October) inter-monsoons the winds are weak and variable. Though the surface circulation of the BoB reverses semi-annually, it does not co-vary exactly with the wind reversal but appears to precede it. The reason for this is variedly attributed to a complex inter-play between the local wind-forcing and the remote-forcing via coastally trapped Kelvin wave and westward propagation of the Rossby waves in the open BoB (Yu et al., 1991; Prasanna Kumar & Unnikrishnan, 1995; McCreary et al., 1996; Eigenheer & Quadfasel, 2000). The basin-wide upper ocean circulation in the BoB is eddy dominated (Nuncio & Prasanna Kumar, 2012).

The co-existence of several oceanographic features stated above and schematically presented in Figure 1 make the BoB a natural laboratory for learning the interactions among the hydrosphere, atmosphere, geosphere and the biosphere. This has attracted numerous researchers and marine scientists to conduct study in this region as is evident from the references cited above. In the past, several studies attempted to understand the upper ocean variability in the BoB and/or in the Indian Ocean including the BoB. These studies were primarily focused on examining how the mixed layer (ML), barrier layer (BL) and upper layer thermal structure had responded to various external and internal forcings. Broadly, these studies can be divided into three categories-those based on (i) in-situ data collected during one or more individual oceanographic expeditions, (ii) climatological data on a regular geographic grid, and (iii) data from ocean models. Studies by various authors under these three categories are summarised in Table 1. It is amply evident from the review of the earlier studies that a reasonably good understanding of the variability of ML and BL exists in the BoB on a seasonal to inter-annual time scales. There also exists fair amount of understanding of the ocean-atmospheric processes that controls the formation and behaviour of the ML and the BL in the BoB. However, a holistic understanding of the seasonal variability of the upper ocean encompassing the ML, BL and the isothermal layer (IL) in the BoB is yet elusive. Also, the spatial structure of the temporal variation of these parameters on a seasonal time-scale, especially in the

northern BoB, is poorly understood. This is mainly due to inadequate spatial coverage of in-situ data in the BoB. This had limited our understanding of the upper ocean variability in greater details. The recent availability of a high-resolution in-situ global oceanographic dataset motivated the present study, allowing us to examine the upper ocean variability on a seasonal time-scale and the processes that contributed to those changes.

Table 1: List of research by different authors focusing on the mixed layer (ML) and barrier layer (BL) in the Bay of Bengal (BoB) and/or BoB as a part of the Indian Ocean using individual oceanographic expedition data, climatological data, and data from ocean model. AS-Arabian Sea; CTD-conductivity-temperature-depth; IO-Indian Ocean; MLD-Mixed Layer Depth; MOODS-Master Oceanographic Observations Data Set; NIO-North Indian Ocean; OGCM- Ocean General Circulation Model; RAMA-Research Moored Array for African-Asian-Australian Monsoon Analysis and Prediction; ROMS-Regional Ocean Modelling System; WOA-World Ocean Atlas.

Sl. No	Studies of mixed layer (ML) and barrier layer (BL) based on data from		
	In situ measurements	Climatology	Ocean model
1.	Murty et al. (1996) Time evolution of ML at 20°N, 89°E in the northern BoB during southwest monsoon was studied using time-series data from August to September 1990.	Rao et al. (1989) Tropical IO MLD was studied using data from MOODS climatology on 2° latitude x 2° longitude grid for the period 1948-1981.	McCreary et al. (1993) Dynamics and thermodynamics of ML physics in the IO was studied using a 2½ layer reduced gravity model.
2.	Gopalakrishna et al. (1988) Effect of wind on ML in the NIO was studied using in situ data during summer monsoon of 1977 & 1979.	Prasanna Kumar & Unnikrishnan (1995) Seasonal cycle of temperature and wave phenomena in the upper layers of the BoB was studied using data from WOA1982 climatology on 1° latitude x 1° longitude grid.	Behera (1998) Response of the ML to cyclone in the BoB was studied using a 1½ layer reduced gravity model.
3.	Gopalakrishna et al. (2002) Impact of fresh water plume on ML in the northern BoB was studied during summer monsoon 1991.	Unnikrishnan et al. (1997) The phase and amplitude of the annual and semi-annual cycle of temperature in the IO was studied using temperature data from WOA1982 climatology on 1° latitude x 1° longitude grid.	Han et al. (2001) Influence of freshwater flux and river runoff on the dynamics, thermodynamics and ML physics in the BoB was studied using a 4½ layer model.
4.	Vinayachandran et al. (2002) Formation of BL during summer monsoon in the BoB was studied based on time series observation at 17.5°N, 89°E from 27 July to 6 August 1999.	Rao & Sivakumar (2000) Annual and semi-annual variability of the thermal structure and heat budget of ML in tropical IO was studied using data from WOA1994 climatology on 1° latitude x 1° longitude grid.	Prasad (2004) Mechanism governing the MLD along a transect in the central BoB and AS was studied using 1-D model.
5.	Swain et al. (2003) Effect of wind and waves on MLD in the central BoB (13°N, 87°E) was studied using time series data during July-August of 1999.	Shenoi et al. (2002) ML heat budget of the AS & BoB was studied using data from WOA1994 climatology on a 1° latitude x 1° longitude grid.	Vinayachandran & Kurian (2007) Structure and variability of ML and BL during summer monsoon in the BoB was studied using OGCM and in situ data.
6.	Maheswaran (2004) Using data from the west and east coast of India studied ML.	Rao & Sivakumar (2003) Seasonal cycle of salinity and its influence on seasonal evolution of MLD in NIO was studied using data from WOA1998 climatology on a 1° latitude x 1° longitude grid.	de Boyer Montegut et al. (2007) Seasonal and inter-annual variability of ML heat budget in the NIO was studied using OGCM.

7.	Thadathil et al. (2007) Seasonal variability of BL in the BoB was studied using Argo data from August 2002 to September 2006.	Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar (2006) Seasonal variability of MLD in the central BoB and its impacts on nutrients and chlorophyll were studied by creating a climatology of temperature and salinity on a 4° latitude x 2° longitude grid by combining ship observations from WOA1994 data (1900-92) and hydro cast & CTD data from Indian research ships (1976-92). Nitrate and chlorophyll from individual profile data from Indian research ships during 1951 to 1997.	Keerthi et al. (2012) Inter-annual variability of the ML in the tropical IO was studied using eddy-permitting OGCM.
8.	Girishkumar et al. (2017) ML temperature budget in the central BoB was studied using time-series data from RAMA mooring at 8°N, 12°N & 15°N along 90°E during 2007/2008 to 2016.	Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar (2014) Basin-scale seasonal variability of MLD in the BoB and its association with chlorophyll was studied by creating a climatology on a 1° latitude by 1° longitude grid by combining hydro-cast data (1919-2000) and CTD data (1972-2003) from world ocean data base, Indian research ship hydro-cast (1972-1996), CTD (1979-2006) and Argo (2002-2007) data.	Sen et al. (2021) Air-sea interaction processes and ML variability was studied during 2013-2014 using ROMS simulation validated by RAMA buoy data.
9.	George et al. (2019) Mechanisms of formation and dissipation of BL in the BoB at 8°N, 89°E was studied using time series data from 4 to 14 July 2016.	Kumari et al. (2018) Seasonal and interannual variability of BL in the BoB was studied using 1/4° resolution, 3-D temperature and salinity fields derived from objectively analysed monthly gridded ocean analysis data from a combination of satellite and in situ observations during 1993-2012.	
10.	Bohman & Gordon (2022) Evolution of ML in high and low sea level anomaly in the BoB was studied during 2015-2018 using Argo, reanalysis and altimeter data.		
11.	Gulakaram et al. (2024) ML variations near mesoscale eddies in the BoB was studied using satellite altimeter and Argo data.		

Objectives and Study Area

The objectives of the present study are:

- To decipher the latitudinal structure of the upper ocean seasonal variability;
- To examine the atmospheric forcing and processes controlling it;
- To understand the role of cloud cover in cooling the SST.

The domain selected for the present study is the central BoB along 88° E longitude and latitude from 5° to 20°N (white dotted-line in Figure 1). The reasons for selecting a north-south section along the central BoB for the study are:

- The variability of the ocean is more pronounced in a meridional (north-south) direction than the zonal (east-west) direction,
- Studying the variability along the central BoB would possibly eliminate the effect of land boundary.

Hence, the selected domain will enable to meet the objectives of the study.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram depicts the characteristic features and processes in the BoB. The light blue and yellow patch in the north denote the fresh water flux from river run-off. The white dotted vertical line in the central BoB is the domain where data were analysed along 88°E from 5° to 20°N. The thin grey band with grey arrows along the coastal boundary is the coastally trapped Kelvin wave, while the thin blue arrows in the zonal direction is the westward propagating Rossby wave. The red/blue-disk-with-curved arrow is the warm-core/cold-core eddy. The tropical cyclone is shown as a patch of anti-clockwise bands with red-yellow-green-blue colours. During summer (southwest) monsoon (June-September) the Southwest Monsoon Current (SWMC, red broad arrows) transports high salinity waters from the Arabian Sea (AS) into the BoB (curved broad red band with arrow head) and in winter (northeast) monsoon (November-February) the East India Coastal Current (EICC, thin white arrows) and North Equatorial Current (NEC, blue broad arrows) transports low salinity waters from the BoB into the eastern AS (curved blue band with arrow head).

2. Data and Methodology

In the present study, data pertaining to both oceanic and atmospheric parameters from a variety of sources were used. A high-resolution climatology of in-situ temperature and salinity data for the global ocean on a $\frac{1}{4}$ degree grid was extracted from the latest World Ocean Atlas 2023 (WOA 2023) which contains objectively analysed and quality-controlled data based on profile data from the World Ocean Database. Additional information on temperature and salinity data documentation can be found in Locarnini et al. (2024) and Reagan et al. (2024), respectively. The monthly mean climatology of temperature and salinity data were downloaded from surface to 1500 m depth for the period 1955 to 2022 in a NetCDF format from the National Oceanic & Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) website (<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/world-ocean-atlas-2023/bin/woa23.pl>). This data was further used to calculate the density (UNESCO, 1981), isothermal layer thickness (ILT) and mixed layer depth (MLD). The ILT (Figure 2) was calculated by

finding the depth at which the sea surface temperature (SST) drops by 0.5° C using equation (1):

$$ILT (m) = SST - 0.5^{\circ}C \quad (1)$$

The MLD is defined as the depth at which in situ density is in excess of sea surface density (SSD) by 0.2 kg/m³ (Figure 2), following Kara et al. (2000) where the MLD is constructed using a density variability ($D\sigma$) that is determined by the corresponding temperature change DT (1°C) holding salinity constant. It was calculated numerically using equation (2).

$$MLD (m) = SSD + 0.2 \text{ kg/m}^3 \quad (2)$$

The barrier layer thickness (BLT) is defined as the layer in which the temperature remains constant with increasing depth but salinity increases with increasing depth (Sprintall & Tomczak, 1992). The ILT and MLD is further used to calculate BLT using equation (3):

$$BLT (m) = ILT - MLD \quad (3)$$

Figure 2: Vertical profiles of temperature (°C, red solid line), salinity (blue solid line) and density (kg/m³, green solid line) in the upper 150 m in the BoB at 12°N, 86°E. The sea surface temperature (SST, °C), sea surface salinity (SSS, psu), sea surface density (SSD, kg/m³), isothermal layer thickness (ILT, m), mixed layer depth (MLD, m) and barrier layer thickness (BLT, m) are also displayed.

Graphically, the SST, SSS, SSD, ILT, MLD and BLT are displayed in Figure 2. The density data was further used for the calculation of static stability parameter (E) in the upper 100 m following Pond & Pickard (1983) using equation (4):

$$E \text{ (m}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\delta \rho}{\delta z} \quad (4)$$

Here, E is the static stability parameter (m^{-1}), ρ is sea water density (kg/m^3), and z is the sea-water depth (m).

The atmospheric parameters used in the present study were net heat flux (NHF), wind speed, evaporation and precipitation. The monthly mean NHF (W/m^2) data having a spatial resolution of 0.33×0.33 degrees longitude by latitude was from National Center for Environmental Prediction (NCEP) atmospheric Reanalysis 2 and was downloaded from Asia Pacific Data Research Center (APDRC) website: (<https://apdrc.soest.hawaii.edu/las/v6/analysis?var=17703>) for the period from 1980 to 2022. Using this data the climatological monthly mean values of NHF were computed.

The monthly mean data on u (zonal) and v (meridional) components of the wind (m/s) at 10 m height from European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Reanalysis v5 (ERA5) global data was extracted from APDRC website (<https://apdrc.soest.hawaii.edu/las/v6/constrain?var=16465>) for the period from 1980 to 2022. The data has a spatial resolution of 0.25×0.25 degrees longitude by latitude. Using this data the climatological monthly mean values of u and v winds were computed. These data were further used for the computation of scalar wind using equation (5):

$$\text{Wind Speed (m/s)} = \sqrt{(u^2 + v^2)} \quad (5)$$

The daily evaporation (m), total precipitation (m) and total cloud cover (dimensionless) data were from ERA5 global data having a spatial resolution of 0.25×0.25 degrees longitude by latitude. These data were extracted from Copernicus Climate Change Service website for the period from 1980 to 2022 (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=form>). The daily data was converted into monthly data and the climatological monthly mean values of evaporation (E) and precipitation (P) were computed as mm/day. The climatological monthly mean values of cloud cover were dimension less and the values vary from 0 to 1. Finally, the freshwater flux was computed using equation (6):

$$\text{Freshwater Flux (mm/day)} = E - P \quad (6)$$

The standard deviation of all the above-mentioned parameters was computed using equation (7):

$$\text{SD} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (7)$$

Here “n” is the number of data, “ x_i ” is the data and “ \bar{x} ” is the mean of the data.

In order to quantitatively determine the association of MLD, ILT and BLT with other ocean-atmospheric variables such as wind speed (WS), NHF, E-P, cloud cover and static stability, partial correlations were computed by calculating the correlation matrix and inverse matrix (Stuart et al., 2010). Partial correlation removes the influence of other variables by calculating the relationship between two variables while holding the effects of other variables constant.

We have used cubic spline interpolation (Carl de Boor, 1978) while preparing the time-latitudinal plots of all seven oceanic (SST, SSS, SSD, ILT, MLD, BLT, static stability parameter) and four atmospheric (wind, NHF, E-P, cloud cover) parameters.

3. Results and Discussion

At first, the upper ocean variability was studied by examining the changes in the surface and subsurface parameters which are presented under 3.1. The atmospheric forcing was analysed and presented under 3.2. Finally, the factors responsible for the observed upper ocean variability was presented under 3.3. In the present study seasons are classified following Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar (2014) and given below:

Winter monsoon or Northeast monsoon: November to February.

Spring inter-monsoon: March to May.

Summer monsoon or Southwest monsoon: June to August.

Fall inter-monsoon: September to October.

3.1. Upper Ocean Variability

In order to understand the upper ocean changes on a seasonal time scale the monthly mean variation of oceanic parameters were analysed in two ways. Firstly, the latitude averaged monthly values were plotted to decipher the seasonal cycle. Secondly, the time-latitude plots of all the oceanic parameters were prepared to understand the spatial variation of the seasonal cycle.

3.1.1. Latitude-Averaged Seasonal Cycle of Upper Ocean Parameters

The upper ocean parameters analysed for the present study along 88° E and averaged from latitudes 5° to 20° N were broadly categorised into: (1) the surface parameters such as SST, SSS, and SSD (2) subsurface parameters such as ILT, MLD and BLT. In the present study the magnitude of seasonal variability of all the parameters were calculated as the difference between the maximum and minimum values and designated as the magnitude of the seasonal variability.

3.1.1.1. Surface Parameters

The monthly mean climatology of SST showed a strong bi-modal distribution with two periods of warming and cooling in a year (Figure 3a). The seasonal cycle starts with the coolest SST of 27.3°C in the month of January, followed by a warming phase with warmest

SST of 29.8°C in May. This was followed by a secondary cooling with a lowest SST of 28.8°C in August and subsequent warming with a secondary maximum SST of 29.1°C in October. The magnitude of seasonal variability of SST was 2.5°C. The standard deviation of SST was the largest during the winter month of February (2.0°C), while it was the smallest during the southwest monsoon month of July (0.1°C). In general, the standard deviations were greater during winter monsoon season and smaller during later part of spring inter-monsoon and summer monsoon. This indicated that the seasonal variability of surface temperature had large spatial variation during winter monsoon.

Figure 3: Monthly mean climatology of latitude (5°-20°N) averaged (a) sea surface temperature (SST, °C), (b) sea surface salinity (SSS, psu) and (c) sea surface density (SSD, kg/m³) along 88°E in the Bay of Bengal (BoB). The vertical lines represent the standard deviations from the mean. The data are from WOA 2023.

The monthly mean climatology of SSS showed a weak bi-modal distribution with two periods of high and low salinity in a year (Figure 3b). The primary high was in June, with a value of 33.32 psu, and the secondary high was in December, with a value of 33.28 psu. The primary low was in October, with a value of 32.34 psu, while the secondary low was in February, with a value of 32.83 psu. The magnitude of the seasonal variability of SSS was 0.98 psu. Unlike temperature the standard deviation of salinity showed a large value all through the year. This indicated that seasonal cycle of surface salinity had a large spatial variation. The highest variability occurred in October (3.70 psu), while the lowest variability was in June (0.70 psu).

The monthly mean climatology of SSD was similar to that of SSS, but the difference was that the magnitude of the bi-modal variability was more pronounced in SSD (Figure 3c). Again, unlike the SSS the secondary minimum in February was shifted to March for SSD. The highest surface density occurred in January with a value of 1021.5 kg/m³ and the lowest in October with a value of 1020.3 kg/m³. The secondary high surface density was in July with a value of 1020.82 kg/m³ followed by a secondary low during April-May with a value of 1020.34 kg/m³. The magnitude of the seasonal variability of SSD was 1.12 kg/m³. The standard deviation also showed a pattern similar to that of SSS, with largest variability in October (3.00 kg/m³) but the smallest was in March (1.00 kg/m³).

3.1.1.2. Subsurface Parameters

The monthly mean climatology of both ILT (Figure 4a) and MLD (Figure 4b) showed a strong bi-modal distribution, with the highest ILT and deepest MLD in February and July with values of 72.9 m and 24.5 m, respectively. In April and October, the thinnest ILT and shallowest MLD were 22.3 m and 11.4 m, respectively. The secondary high ILT and deep MLD occurred in July and January with values 45.0 m and 21.1 m respectively. The secondary low ILT and shallow MLD occurred in October and April, respectively, with values of 33.0 m and 12.0 m, respectively. The similar pattern of variability in both ILT and MLD to that of SST suggested a strong relationship between them. The magnitude of the seasonal variability of ILT and MLD were 50.6 m and 13.0 m respectively. These values were comparable with those obtained by Kumari et al. (2018). The co-occurrence of secondary shallow MLD during March-April with warmest SST suggests the dominant role of surface temperature in regulating the MLD during spring inter-monsoon. Similarly, the co-occurrence of shallowest MLD in October with lowest SSS and secondary highest SST suggested the combined role of surface salinity and temperature in controlling the MLD during fall inter-monsoon.

Figure 4: Monthly mean climatology of latitude (5° - 20° N) averaged (a) isothermal layer thickness (ILT, m), (b) mixed layer depth (MLD, m) and (c) barrier layer thickness (BLT, m) along 88° E in the Bay of Bengal (BoB). The vertical lines are the standard deviations from the mean. The data are from WOA 2023.

The monthly mean climatology of BLT showed a weak bi-modal distribution (Figure 4c), which resembled with the ones of SST and SSS. The BLT demonstrated a direct relationship with SST and an inverse relationship with SSS. The highest BLT was in February with a value of 55.7 m and the lowest in April with a value of 10.5 m. The secondary high of 20.5 was in August, while the secondary low was in June with a value of 19.3 m. The magnitude of the seasonal variability of BLT was 45.2 m. The standard deviation of ILT, MLD and BLT (Figure 4a-c) showed high values, implying that the seasonal variability had a large spatial variation for all three parameters.

3.1.2. Time-Latitudinal Variability of Upper Ocean Parameters

After analysing and deciphering the latitude-averaged seasonal cycle of upper ocean

parameters, their spatial structure was examined to understand how the seasonal cycle varies latitudinally. To achieve this, we plotted the monthly mean climatology of upper ocean parameters along 88°E longitude and from 5° to 20°N latitude. For ease of analysis, we again, subdivided the upper ocean parameters into surface and subsurface

3.1.2.1. Surface Parameters

Figure 5a shows that the SST time-latitude plot changed every six months, with two periods of warm and cold SSTs. This is similar to the pattern of bi-modal variability seen in the seasonal cycle in latitude-averaged SST (Figure 3a). However, the spatial structure of the warming and cooling was not uniform across the latitudes. Using SST greater than 29°C as an indicator of warm surface temperature, we observed the primary warming from April to June in the northern BoB, north of 15°N, and from March to June in the southern BoB, south of 15°N. The highest SST of 30°C occurred during April in the southern BoB and in May in the northern BoB. However, the secondary warming during September-October was more pronounced towards the north of 10°N with a maximum value of 29.6°C in October. During the primary warming period, the figure showed very little north-south variation in SST, while there was a noticeable spatial difference during the secondary warm period. The latitude-averaged SST during April-May and October, respectively, showed the least and most noticeable standard deviation (Figure 3a). If SST less than 26.5°C is taken as an indicator of cool surface temperature, two points emerges: first, the primary cooling was confined to latitudes north of 15°N and cooling was seen during November to March with the coldest SST of 25.4°C in January (Figure 5a). The figure showed the greatest meridional difference in SST during winter, which explains the large standard deviations during this period. The secondary cool SST occurred from July to September in the northern BoB, and it continued until October in the south. However, Figure 3a shows a small standard deviation, indicating that the SST did not show much north-south variation during September-October. The magnitude of the seasonal variation in SST was the largest in the north BoB with a value of 4.6°C, while in the southern part of the BoB it was the smallest with a value of 1.2°C. The reasons for the observed variabilities were discussed under section 3.3.

Figure 5: Time-latitude plot of monthly mean climatology of (a) sea surface temperature

(SST, °C), (b) sea surface salinity (SSS, psu) and (c) sea surface density (SSD, kg/m³) along 88° E from 5°-20°N in the Bay of Bengal (BoB). The data are from WOA2023.

The time-latitude plot of SSS showed a distinct difference in the seasonal cycle between northern and southern BoB (Figure 5b). Northern BoB, north of 15°N, the seasonal cycle was strong and annual, with one high and one low salinity value. The lowest salinity was in October with a value of 28.2 psu, while the highest salinity of 33.0 psu was in June. Despite the persistent low salinity, defined as the region within the 32.0 psu salinity contour, from July to March, there were two distinct instances of low salinity: one in August with a value of 29.0 psu and the other in October with a value of 28.2 psu. This would need an explanation. The low salinity in August was the direct response to the freshwater flux from the river discharge, while that in October was linked to the advection of low salinity waters by the prevailing circulation. In the central and southern BoB, between 5 to 15° N, the seasonal cycle was semi-annual but weak with two high and two low salinity peaks (Figure 5b). Though the primary and secondary low salinity occurred in October and April respectively, both had the same value of 32.6 psu. Similarly, the primary and secondary high occurred in September and January respectively, but both had the same value of 34.2 psu. Note that the magnitude of SSS seasonal variability was highest in the northern BoB with a value of 4.8 psu, and in the central and southern parts of BoB it was 1.6 psu. The surface salinity showed significant spatial variation throughout the year, as evidenced by the large standard deviations in Figure 3b.

SSD's pattern of time-latitude variability (Figure 5c) closely resembled that of SSS, with large spatial variation throughout the year, especially in the northern BoB. Figure 3c displays these spatial variations as large standard deviations. Unlike the surface salinity, the surface density showed a semi-annual cycle across the latitude. The magnitude of variability was highest in the northern BoB, and it decreased as it moved south. In the northern BoB, north of 15°N, the primary low density was in October with a value of 1016.4 kg/m³ and the secondary low was in May with a value of 1020.0 kg/m³. Though the primary and secondary high densities occurred in January and July, respectively, both had the same value of 1020.8 kg/m³. The semi-annual cycle was more noticeable in the central and southern BoB, between 5° to 15° N. There were two high and two low densities that were well separated in time (Figure 5c). The primary low density was in April with a value of 1019.8 kg/m³ and the secondary low was in October with a value of 1020 kg/m³. Similar to the northern BoB, the primary and secondary high densities occurred at different times, January and September, respectively, but had the same value of 1021.6 kg/m³. The magnitude of the seasonal change of SSD was the highest in the north with 4.8 kg/m³ and in the central and southern BoB it was 2.0 kg/m³.

3.1.2.2. Subsurface Parameters

The time-latitude distribution of ILT showed strong annual variability in the northern

BoB, north of 17°N , with low thickness varying from 15 to 35 m during April to October and high thickness from November to March with the highest value of 85 m occurring in February (Figure 6a). In the central and southern BoB, between 5° to 17°N , the variability was a strong semi-annual with thickest ILT of 80 m in February and secondary high thickness of 65 m in July. The lowest thickness occurred in April with a value of 20 m, followed by the second lowest thickness of 25 m in October. This was consistent with latitude-averaged monthly ILT in Figure 4a. The wide spatial variations of ILT across the latitudes were seen as large standard deviations in Figure 4a. The magnitudes of the annual and semi-annual variabilities in ILT in the BoB were 70 m and 60 m respectively.

Figure 6: Time-latitude plot of monthly mean climatology of (a) isothermal layer thickness (ILT, m), (b) mixed layer depth (MLD, m) and (c) barrier layer thickness (BLT, m) along 88°E from 5° - 20°N in the Bay of Bengal (BoB). The data is from WOA 2023.

The time-latitude distribution of MLD showed weak annual variability in the north (17°N) and a strong semi-annual variability south of it (Figure 6b). North of 17°N the shallowest MLD of 4 m occurred twice, first in August and second in October, while the second shallowest value of 7 m occurred in May. The deepest MLD of 19 m occurred in June. South of 17°N , the deepest MLD of 37 m occurred in July and August, while the shallowest MLD of 7 m occurred in April and October (Figure 6b). In the north, the semi-annual variability of MLD followed more closely with the SSS (Figure 4b), while that in the south followed both the SSS and SST (Figure 4a). This indicated that the spatially differentiated change in the MLD must be due to different forcing mechanisms. The magnitude of the annual variability was 15 m north and 30 m south of 17°N . An earlier study on the seasonal variability of MLD revealed a deficiency in seasonality in the northern BoB, north of 15°N , and a robust semi-annual variability south of 15°N (Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar, 2006). They missed capturing the annual variability in the northern BoB, because of their spatially coarse (2° latitude \times 4° longitude) in-situ data. Mesoscale cold-core eddy signature appears as closed contours of low MLDs in June and October between 6° and 8°N . Similarly, the signature of warm-core eddy appears as

high MLDs in July between 11° and 13°N and in December between 15° and 17°N. Some of these eddy signatures were also visible in the BLT (Figure 6c).

The time-latitude distribution of BLT showed a strong annual variability in the northern BoB north of 17° N and a strong semi-annual variability south of it (Figure 6c). The annual variability in the north was characterised by the thickest BLT during February with a value of 75 m and the thinnest with a value of 10 m was seen in June and September. This gives the magnitude of the annual variability as 65 m. In the south, between 5° and 17° N the seasonality was marked by a strong semi-annual variability with the thickest BLT of 75 m in February followed by the second thickest BLT of 40 m in June and October. The lowest BLT of 10 m occurred in March and May, while the second lowest value of 15 m was seen in October (Figure 6c). This gives the magnitude of the semi-annual variability as 65 m. Though numerically BLT is the difference between ILT and MLD, the spatial structure of the seasonal variability of BLT resembled more with the one of ILT. The number of high and low BLT in closed contours which also was seen in ILT and MLD could be the signature of warm (anti-cyclonic) and cold (cyclonic) mesoscale eddies which are ubiquitous in the BoB. To confirm if these are mesoscale eddies a detailed analysis of sea-level height anomaly is necessary (Nuncio & Prasanna Kumar, 2012).

The above-mentioned variability in the spatial structure of the seasonal cycle, especially the meridional behaviour, of the surface and subsurface parameters are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: Magnitude of seasonal variability of SST, SSS, SSD, ILT, MLD and BLT in the central Bay of Bengal (BoB) along longitude 88°E and from latitude 5° to 20°N.

Sl. No	Magnitude of the Seasonal Variability Obtained from		
	Parameter	Latitude-averaged monthly mean climatology	Time-latitude values of monthly mean climatology
1.	SST	Strong semi-annual variability 2.5°C	Semi-annual north of 15°N: 4.6°C Semi-annual south of 15°N: 1.2°C
2.	SSS	Weak semi-annual variability 0.98	Strong annual north of 15°N: 5.2 Weak Semi-annual south of 15°N: 1.6
3.	SSD	Strong semi-annual variability 1.12 kg/m ³	Semi-annual north of 15°N: 4.8 kg/m ³ Semi-annual south of 15°N: 2.0 kg/m ³
4.	ILT	Strong semi-annual variability 50.6 m	Strong annual north of 17°N: 70 m Strong Semi-annual south of 17°N: 60 m
5.	MLD	Strong semi-annual variability 13.1 m	Weak annual north of 17°N: 15 m Strong Semi-annual south of 17°N: 30 m
6.	BLT	Weak semi-annual variability 45.2 m	Strong annual north of 17°N: 65 m Weak Semi-annual south of 17°N: 65 m

3.2. Atmospheric Forcings

In this section the atmospheric forcings were examined to understand the variabilities in the surface and subsurface parameters in the central BoB. The upper ocean is usually forced by the overlying atmosphere through changes in three important fluxes such as

net heat flux, momentum flux and the freshwater flux. The net heat flux (NHF) is a sum of the net downward shortwave radiation from the sun, which is positive as the ocean gains heat, net upward longwave radiation from the ocean, which is negative as the ocean loses heat, the latent heat flux through evaporation, which is negative as the ocean loses heat, and the sensible heat flux, which could be either negative or positive depending on whether the ocean loses heat (negative) or gains heat (positive). The positive NHF implies that the ocean is gaining heat from the incoming shortwave solar radiation. The negative NHF indicates that the ocean is losing heat due to a variety of sources, including long wave radiation from the ocean and both sensible and latent heat losses. The wind exerts a force in the direction of the wind, known as the momentum flux or wind stress. In the present study, we use wind speed as a proxy for wind stress because the magnitude of the wind stress is proportional to the quadratic of the scalar wind, which is the product of air density, drag coefficient, and the quadratic of the wind speed (Large & Pond, 1981). Further, we also use freshwater flux (E-P).

3.2.1. Latitude-Averaged Seasonal Cycle of Atmospheric Parameters

The latitude-averaged wind speed showed a strong semi-annual variability with the maximum value of 8.6 m/s in June and the minimum value of 2.2 m/s during October (Figure 7a). The secondary maximum value of 5.0 m/s was in January and secondary minimum value of 2.4 m/s was in April. The primary and secondary wind speed maxima were associated with the southwest and northeast monsoons respectively. The primary and secondary minima were associated with fall and spring inter-monsoons respectively. The large standard deviations all through the year except in May implied a large latitudinal variability in the wind speed (Figure 7a). The time-averaged NHF showed a semi-annual variability (Figure 7b) similar to the wind speed, however, the time of occurrence of maxima and minima of both were different. The primary maxima of +94.6 W/m² occurred during April and the primary minima of -110.4 W/m² in December. The secondary maxima and minima were in October with a value of +33.2 W/m² and in June with a value of -37.8 W/m² (Figure 7b). Note that during the primary and secondary maxima, which occurred during the spring and fall inter-monsoons respectively, the ocean gained heat. In contrast, during both primary and secondary minima, which occurred during summer and winter monsoons, the ocean lost heat. The standard deviation (Figure 7b) showed large values only during winter monsoon period indicating large latitudinal variation in the net heat loss from the ocean. The freshwater flux, unlike the wind speed and NHF, showed an annual variability with the highest value of 3.1 mm/day in January and the second highest value of 2.95 mm/day in February (Figure 7c). The highest value in January and the next highest value in February indicated that the ocean was losing water through evaporation during winter. The lowest value in July (-4.2 mm/day) and second lowest value in September (-4.0 mm/day) indicated that the ocean was gaining water through precipitation. The large standard deviation (Figure 7c), occurring during summer and winter monsoon seasons, indicated large latitudinal variability in evaporation during winter monsoon and precipitation during summer monsoon, respectively.

Figure 7: Monthly mean climatology of latitude (5° - 20° N) averaged (a) wind speed (m/s), (b) net heat flux (NHF, W/m^2) and (c) evaporation minus precipitation (E-P, mm/day) along 88° E in the BoB . The vertical lines are the standard deviations from the mean. The data on wind and E-P are from ERA5, while NHF is from NCEP atmospheric reanalysis 2.

3.2.2. Time-Latitude Variability of Atmospheric Parameters

The spatial structure of the temporal variation of the wind speed (Figure 8a) and the NHF (Figure 8b) inferred from the time-latitude plots reiterated strong semi-annual variability seen in the latitude-averaged wind speed (Figure 7a) and NHF (Figure 7b). The additional information was that though the semi-annual variability was seen across all the latitudes from 5° to 20° N, the magnitudes of both maximum and minimum values differed from that of the latitude-averaged values. For example, the primary and secondary maximum values of wind speeds were 9 m/s and 6 m/s respectively, with no change in their temporal occurrences (Figure 8a). The NHF, during the period of primary high wind speed in summer monsoon and the secondary period in winter monsoon, were associated with a net heat loss from the ocean (Figure 8b). However, highest magnitude of heat loss from ocean occurred not during primary wind speed maxima, but during secondary wind speed maxima. The zero contour means that the heat loss from the ocean equals the heat gain by the ocean. From Figure 8b it can be observed that the net heat loss and net heat gain balances during February and again in October at most latitudes. The highest value of negative NHF-180 W/m^2 occurred in December in the northern BoB, while the second highest negative value of-60 W/m^2 occurred in June in the southern BoB (Figure 8b). This indicated that the highest loss of heat from the ocean during northeast monsoon in the north could be due to the evaporative cooling of wind in the form of latent heat loss. In a similar study, Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar (2006) reported that radiative cooling due to reduced incoming solar radiation along with evaporative cooling by wind was the reason for lowest NHF. The secondary heat loss seen in the central and southern BoB was predominantly due to the latent heat loss by evaporative cooling under strong southwest monsoon winds. This could be the reason for the primary and secondary cooling seen in the SST (Figure 3a, 4a). Similarly, the primary and secondary net heat gained by the ocean during March-April and October was associated with the high incoming solar radiation, as this is the only positive term in the calculation of NHF. This was also manifested

in the time variation of SST (Figure 3a, 5a) as the primary and secondary highest values.

Figure 8: Time-latitude plot of monthly mean climatology of (a) wind speed (m/s), (b) net heat flux (NHF, W/m^2) and (c) evaporation minus precipitation (E-P, mm/day) along $88^\circ E$ in the BoB. The data of wind and E-P are from ERA5, while NHF is from NCEP atmospheric reanalysis 2.

The spatial structure of the temporal variation of E-P inferred from the time-latitude plot (Figure 8c) showed an annual variability similar to that shown by the latitude averaged E-P (Figure 7c). The annual cycle was stronger in the northern BoB in comparison to the south. North of $15^\circ N$, the E-P was negative indicating that precipitation was dominant over evaporation from May, peaked in July with the lowest E-P value of -11 mm/day and diminished by October (Figure 8c). The zero contour indicates that the loss of water from the ocean through evaporation equals the gain of water by the ocean through precipitation. The E-P was positive during November to March indicating excess evaporation over precipitation with the highest value of 5 mm/day in January. In the central and southern regions from 5° to $15^\circ N$, though the variability was annual its magnitude was small. The highest value of excess evaporation remained the same as that of north and occurred in January, while the highest excess precipitation was only -5 mm/day. During June to August the evaporation balanced the precipitation in the region south of $9^\circ N$. The zero contour indicated the balance between evaporation and precipitation. It can be seen from the plot that during March and October the evaporation balances the precipitation. Thus, during winter monsoon evaporation was in excess, in spring inter-monsoon evaporation balanced the precipitation, during summer monsoon precipitation was in excess and in fall inter-monsoon evaporation balanced the precipitation.

3.3. Processes Controlling the Upper Ocean Variability

In this section the processes that controlled the upper ocean variability on a seasonal time-scale was explored based on the insight gained from the above analysis of ocean and atmospheric parameters. The temporal variation of the surface parameter SST and

the subsurface parameter ILT showed great similarity with NHF and to some extent with the wind speed, while the temporal variability of surface parameter SSS and the subsurface parameter BLT showed a close similarity with the E-P. However, the temporal variability of the surface parameter SSD and the subsurface parameter MLD showed great similarity with wind speed and NHF during winter monsoon and with wind speed and E-P during summer monsoon. However, the spatial structure of the temporal variation of both surface and subsurface ocean parameters were complex and showed varied inter-dependence with the atmospheric forcing. This brings up the question of what processes controlled the spatial pattern of variability in the upper ocean parameters?

The spatial structure of the primary warm SST during April-May period (Figure 5a) closely followed the maximum positive NHF during March-April (Figure 8b). The spatial structure of secondary warm SST in October though coincided with the second maximum positive NHF, in the northern BoB this occurred in September and subsequently in the central and southern BoB in October. Note that the wind speed (Figure 8a) during both March-April and September in the north and October in the southern BoB were minimum. The process that led to the primary and secondary peaks in the SST was driven by the primary and secondary peaks in the incoming solar radiation and subsequent heat gain by the ocean. The one-month lag between NHF and SST was the manifestation of thermal lag or thermal inertia of the ocean due to its large heat capacity. The lowest wind speed during the above periods supported the ocean heating as the wind-induced heat loss due to evaporation was the least as could be seen from the fresh water flux E-P, where the values were negative (Figure 8c). The negative NHF during May to August was closely linked to the secondary cooling seen in SST during June to September. The process that mediated the heat loss from the ocean was the evaporative cooling by the strong southwest monsoon winds, which strengthened from May, peaked in July and persisted until September. However, the spatial structure of the fresh water flux showed a strong excess precipitation in the northern BoB, a weak excess precipitation in the central BoB (9°-15°N) and evaporation balancing the precipitation in the southern BoB during southwest monsoon (Figure 8c). Nevertheless, large amount of evaporation occurred during the southwest monsoon period by strong wind, though precipitation overwhelmed evaporation. This implied that though the observed cooling of SST during June to September could arise from the strong evaporation, that alone cannot explain the total cooling of SST during this period. Another process that contributed to the cooling was the cloud cover (Figure 9) associated with southwest monsoon, which showed high values during June to September period (Figure 9a) and was present spatially over the entire latitude from 5° to 20° N (Figure 9b).

The high amount of cloud cover during southwest monsoon reduced the incoming solar radiation and that contributed to the overall cooling during this period. The close correspondence of the spatial structure of NHF (Figure 8b) and SST (Figure 5a) during

November to February suggested that the strongest net heat loss from the ocean was mediated by the strong evaporation (Figure 8c) which started strengthening in November, peaked in January and persisted until March. Though the wind speed during this period had only the secondary high value, they were able to initiate strong evaporation. This is because these winds during November to February were the northeasterly that originated from the land and hence were dry. When these dry winds blow over the BoB, they were able to evaporate high amount of water from the surface of the ocean. In addition to this, the lowest amount of cloud cover during winter monsoon, especially in the north (Figure 9b) supported the outgoing longwave radiation from the ocean and led to subsequent radiative cooling. Along with this, the less amount of incoming solar led to cooling of the upper ocean in the BoB. Our result regarding the NHF driving the seasonal variability of the SST is similar to those reported by earlier studies (Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar, 2006, 2014), the difference being earlier studies have used only in coming short-wave radiation instead of the NHF. The incoming solar radiation is only one component of the NHF and hence do not account for the complete atmospheric forcing that modulates the SST. Our study captured the spatial structure of both the SST and NHF and hence could explain the observed variability in SST in a comprehensive manner.

Figure 9: (a) Monthly mean climatology of latitude (5°-20°N) averaged and (b) time-latitude plot of total cloud cover along 88° E in the Bay of Bengal (BoB). The vertical lines in (a) are the standard deviations from the mean. The cloud cover data are from ERA5.

The spatial structure of the temporal variation of SSS (Figure 5b) in the northern BoB showed a close link with freshwater flux (Figure 8c). The excess precipitation during June to September could explain the presence of low salinity waters during July to September. The persistence of low salinity waters beyond September and up to February

would need another process and points to the role of river discharge in reducing the surface salinity. Earlier studies have shown that river discharge is a dominant forcing in diluting the upper ocean waters in the BoB (Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar, 2006, 2014). The monthly mean climatology of river discharge data from the major rivers such as Ganges, Brahmaputra, Irrawaddy, Godavari and Krishna showed that though the peak discharge from these rivers occurred between July to October, their influence in the northern BoB persisted until February-March period (Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar, 2014). Hence, the persistence of low salinity water in the present study beyond September was mediated by the freshwater input from rivers. Thus, the first low salinity in August was associated with the peak in oceanic precipitation of July inferred from the E-P, while the second lowest value in October was associated with the river runoff. The presence of surface water with comparatively more salinity during March to May could be related to the excess evaporation under the influence of primary heating by incoming solar radiation (Figure 8b). In the central and southern BoB, the semi-annual cycle of SSS closely followed the semi-annual cycle in E-P. In addition to the freshwater flux, the advection of low salinity water from the northern BoB during September to February and high salinity waters of AS origin into the southern part of the BoB during June to September also contributed to the observed semi-annual variability in salinity. Intrusion of high salinity waters from the AS into the BoB has been reported in an earlier study by Narvekar & Prasanna Kumar (2006). Unlike the earlier studies, the present study captured the spatial variability of both SSS and the atmospheric freshwater flux (E-P) and hence could provide a more robust explanation for the north-south difference in the seasonal cycle. One limitation is that the present study did not analyse the river runoff data, instead relied up on the published data.

The spatial structure of the temporal variation of SSD (Figure 5c) greatly resembled the surface salinity (Figure 5b) with the exception that the strong semi-annual variation was noticed all through the latitudes. The presence of low-density water in northern BoB during July to October was due to a combination of excess precipitation (Figure 8c) and river runoff. The high-density water during November to February was due to the winter cooling mediated by the net heat loss from the ocean. As mentioned earlier the cooling was by a combination of processes such as latent heat loss by evaporation and radiative heat loss by outgoing long wave radiation (Figure 8b). However, the primary low-density waters present during April-May was due to the primary heating by incoming solar radiation which was seen in the NHF as the largest positive value (Figure 8b). The secondary high-density waters during June to September was due to cooling by cloud cover (Figure 9b) and increase in salinity by the advection of high salinity waters from the AS (Figure 5b).

Similar to the temperature of the surface ocean, the spatial structure of temporal variation of ILT (Figure 6a) matched closely with NHF (Figure 8b) and to some extent wind speed

(Figure 8a). In the northern BoB, the annual cycle of ILT closely followed the annual cycle of NHF with low ILT when ocean gained heat during March to October and high ILT when ocean lost heat from November to February. In the central and southern BoB, the low ILT coincided with the period of primary and secondary heating and low wind speeds, while the thick ILT were associated with primary and secondary cooling and higher wind speeds. Thus, the primary process that controlled the ILT was the NHF.

To understand the processes that controlled the spatial structure of the temporal variation in MLD (Figure 6b) it is important to examine the atmospheric forcings in the context of upper ocean stability and stratification, since both impact the vertical mixing. Hence, the latitude-averaged monthly mean (Figure 10a) and time-latitude variation (Figure 10b) of static stability parameter were plotted. In the northern BoB the persistence of thin MLD showed close link to (1) excess precipitation during July to September (Figure 8c) through lowering of salinity, (2) river discharge from October to November and low salinity. Both led to the perennial presence of low salinity water in the northern BoB and made the upper water column highly stratified, as inferred from the high values of the static stability parameter (Figure 10b).

Figure 10: Monthly mean climatology of (a) latitude (5°-20°N) averaged and (b) time-latitude plot of upper 100 m static stability parameter ($\times 10^{-5}, \text{m}^{-1}$) along 88° E in the Bay of Bengal (BoB). The vertical lines in (a) are the standard deviations from the mean. The density was calculated from the temperature and salinity data from WOA 2023.

This underscored the combined role of freshwater flux and river runoff in making the upper ocean highly stratified. Even the high wind speed associated with southwest monsoon (Figure 8a) was unable to break this stratification and deepen the mixed layer. During winter monsoon, though the stratification decreased due to cooling, the northeast monsoon

winds with reduced speeds were unable to increase the MLD substantially through vertical mixing. In the central and southern BoB, the thick MLD during June to September was driven by a combination of processes such as the reduction in SST and increase in SSS. The cooling was due to latent heat loss via evaporation under strong winds and radiative heat loss was due to reduced incoming solar radiation via increased cloud cover. Increase in the SSS was due to advection of high salinity waters from the AS. Both of these increased the density of the upper water column and decreased the stratification as inferred from the low values of static stability parameter (Figure 10b). The strong southwest monsoon winds were able to increase vertical mixing and deepen the mixed layer. The secondary increase in the MLD during winter monsoon was due to a combination of processes that increased the surface density. Firstly, the reduction in the incoming radiation, increase in the latent heat flux by large-scale evaporation under dry northeasterly winds, and increased out-going longwave radiation under less cloud cover, all of which led to the cooling of surface ocean. Secondly, the enhanced evaporation also led to an increase in the surface salinity. The resulting increase in the surface density reduced the static stability and the northeast monsoon winds with second maximum speed were able to break the stratification and initiate deep vertical mixing. During the spring and fall inter-monsoons, the primary and secondary heating from March to May and September-October made the upper ocean waters warm and more stable (Figure 9b). Hence, the prevailing weak winds were unable to break the strong stratification and induce deep mixing.

The processes that led to the semi-annual variability in BLT was a combination of NHF and freshwater flux in the northern BoB. In the central and southern BoB, the semi-annual variability of BLT was controlled by different processes during different period. During southwest monsoon period, strong winds, freshwater flux, advection of low salinity water from the northern BoB and high salinity waters of AS origin from the southern BoB contributed to variability in the BLT. During winter monsoon NHF, freshwater flux and advection of low salinity waters from the northern BoB played a role in the variation of BLT. The BLT during spring and fall inter-monsoons was affected by NHF and freshwater flux.

Finally, to understand the relative importance of each of the forcings such wind speed, NHF, E-P, cloud cover and static stability on MLD, ILT and BLT, partial correlations were computed and presented in Table 3.

The MLD showed high linear correlation with wind, NHF, cloud cover and to a lesser extent with static stability (Table 3a). Though the correlation with static stability was low, it was statistically significant at 99% confidence level. Note that both NHF and static stability were negatively correlated with MLD, which means that MLD is inversely related with NHF and static stability. The ILT also showed an inverse correlation with NHF, which were statistically significant at 99% confidence level (Table 3b).

Table 3: Partial correlation of (a) mixed layer depth (MLD), (b) isothermal layer thickness (ILT), and (c) barrier layer thickness (BLT) with five variables viz. wind speed (WS), net heat flux (NHF), evaporation minus precipitation (E-P), cloud cover, and static stability. All parameters were averaged from 5°N to 20°N along 88°E. Numbers in bold font indicates statistically significant correlation at 99% confidence level (p-values <0.01) based on t-test.

(a)						
Partial correlation	MLD	WS	NHF	E-P	Cloud cover	Static stability
MLD	1					
WS	0.9	1				
NHF	-0.7	-0.4	1			
E-P	-0.4	0.6	0.04	1		
Cloud cover	0.6	0.8	-0.2	0.9	1	
Static stability	-0.4	-0.1	0.4	-0.7	0.5	1
(b)						
Partial correlation	MLD	WS	NHF	E-P	Cloud cover	Static stability
MLD	1					
WS	0.1	1				
NHF	-0.6	-0.4	1			
E-P	0.4	0.6	0.04	1		
Cloud cover	-0.3	0.8	-0.2	0.9	1	
Static stability	-0.8	-0.1	0.4	-0.7	0.4	1
(c)						
Partial correlation	MLD	WS	NHF	E-P	Cloud cover	Static stability
MLD	1					
WS	-0.1	1				
NHF	-0.5	-0.4	1			
E-P	-0.6	0.6	0.03	1		
Cloud cover	0.5	0.8	-0.2	0.9	1	
Static stability	-0.8	-0.1	-0.1	-0.7	0.5	1

However, the BLT showed an inverse correlation with E-P and a direct correlation with static stability (Table 3c). In all the three cases (Table 3 a, b, c) wind speed played a dominant role in controlling the E-P and cloud cover, while static stability played important role in controlling MLD, ILT and BLT. The cloud cover played a dominant role in regulating the wind speed and E-P.

4. Summary and Conclusion

Upper ocean variability in the BoB has been an area of considerable interest to researchers; however, a major limitation was the inadequate spatial and temporal coverage of the available regional data. This led to the lack of holistic understanding of the upper ocean variability, particularly on a seasonal time-scale. In the present study using the recently released high resolution monthly mean climatology of global ocean temperature and salinity data on a $\frac{1}{4}$ degree grid in the form of the World Ocean Atlas 2023, the upper ocean variability was studied on a seasonal time-scale. The ocean data were grouped into surface (SST, SSS, SSD) and subsurface (ILT, MLD, BLT) parameters. To assess their seasonal variability latitude-averaged monthly means were analysed. Further, time-latitude plots were used to examine the spatial structure of the seasonal cycle. To understand the ocean-atmospheric interactions driving this variability, atmospheric data on wind speed, NHF, freshwater flux and cloud coverage were analysed. Additionally, static stability was also computed to assess stratification in the upper 100 m of the water column.

All the three surface parameters showed a bi-modal seasonal pattern, with SST having the highest and SSS the lowest latitude-averaged variability. Large standard deviations indicated notable spatial variation. Subsurface parameters also exhibited bi-modal seasonal cycles, with ILT showing the greatest variability, followed by BLT and MLD, all displaying significant spatial differences. The time-latitude distribution of SST showed a strong semi-annual variability, with primary warming peak in April–May and secondary warming peak in October. The primary warming was evident across all latitudes, while the secondary peak was more pronounced in the north. Primary cooling occurred in January, mainly in the north, while secondary cooling appeared in July in the northern BoB and in September in the south. Primary and secondary warming were driven by peaks in incoming solar radiation during March–April and September–October, respectively, with low wind speeds reducing evaporative heat loss. A one-month lag between NHF and SST reflected the ocean’s thermal inertia. The role of cloud cover in regulating the cooling of upper ocean during both winter and summer monsoon are hither to not be explored by earlier researchers. Unlike SST, the seasonal cycle of SSS exhibited two distinct spatial patterns. In the northern BoB, a strong annual cycle was observed, with lowest salinity in October and highest in June. In contrast, the central and southern BoB showed a weaker semi-annual cycle with two salinity highs and lows. These patterns closely resembled with the one of freshwater flux and river runoff. In the north, low salinity from July to September was driven by excess rainfall, while the

persistence of low salinity until February was due to river discharge from the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Irrawaddy. In the central and southern BoB, the semi-annual SSS cycle corresponded with the E–P variability. Additionally, the southward advection of low-salinity water from the north (September–February) and the intrusion of High-Salinity Arabian Sea Water into the southern BoB (June–September) contributed to the semi-annual pattern. The surface density exhibited a pronounced semi-annual cycle across all latitudes, closely resembling the variability in surface salinity. An exception occurred in March–April, when increased solar heating dominated density changes across the region. The amplitude of semi-annual variability was over twice as large in the northern BoB compared to the south.

The ILT showed strong annual variability in the north and semi-annual variability in the central and southern BoB. This pattern was regulated by similar processes as SST. In the north, ILT was influenced mainly by NHF and wind-driven heat loss. In the south, semi-annual ILT variability during the monsoons was influenced by NHF, cloud cover, and wind speed, while solar radiation dominated during spring and fall inter-monsoons.

Unlike the ILT, the time-latitude distribution of MLD showed a weak annual variation in the north and a strong semi-annual variation in the south. However, the timing of deepest and shallowest MLDs differed between regions. In the north, MLD changes closely followed surface salinity, indicating strong freshwater flux control. Persistent shallow MLDs from July to November were driven by excess rainfall (July–September) and advection of river discharge waters (October–November). Despite high southwest monsoon winds, strong stratification prevented deep mixing. Similarly, during the winter monsoon, reduced wind speeds under northeast monsoon conditions were insufficient to erode stratification. In the central and southern BoB, summer monsoon condition, characterized by cooler, saltier surface waters and strong wind, reduced stability and promoted deep mixing. Thick MLDs in this region were due to increased cloud cover and wind speed, both of which cooled the upper ocean. Additionally, the intrusion of high salinity Arabian Sea Waters further decreased static stability. During the winter monsoon, thick MLDs also developed due to surface cooling and salinity increase driven by: (1) evaporation and latent heat loss under northeast monsoon winds, (2) reduced solar radiation, and (3) enhanced longwave radiation loss under clear skies. These processes increased surface density, reduced stratification, and, together with strong winds, deepened the mixed layer. The seasonal variability of BLT, the latter being the difference between the ILT and MLD, was controlled by processes governing both. BLT exhibited strong annual variability in the north and weaker semi-annual variability in the south, similar to that of ILT. Both net heat flux and freshwater flux played key roles in shaping its spatial structure. The most pronounced changes in BLT occurred during the winter monsoon. In conclusion, this study revealed the detailed latitudinal structure of the upper ocean's seasonal cycle, enabled by high-resolution thermohaline data. It also

uniquely highlighted the role of cloud cover in cooling SST during winter and summer monsoon, a mechanism previously unexplored. This cooling reduced static stability and enhanced mixed layer depth through deep mixing. Further research with additional observations and model output is needed to quantify the role of cloud cover in cooling SST during both summer and winter monsoons.

One of the limitations of the study is the use of data having different spatial resolutions for ocean and atmospheric parameters. For example, the spatial resolution of NHF is slightly coarser than the spatial resolution of all other data used in the present study. Another limitation is the lack of detailed quantification of the triggering mechanisms, both atmospheric and oceanic. Though the present study identifies processes that regulate the spatial structure of the seasonal cycle, modelling studies are needed for the quantifying the specific role of each of the analysed forcings.

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